

Analysing the Environmental, Economic and Health Implications of the Failure of Enforcement of Zero Gas Flaring Policy for the Niger Delta, Nigeria¹

Ernest Tooche Aniche, PhD

Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

anicheet@fuotuoche.edu.ng

ORCID: 0000-0002-2449-4717

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19401400>

Abstract

The study systematically examined the environmental, economic, and health implications of the failure to enforce zero-gas flaring in the core Niger Delta, specifically in Bayelsa, Delta, and Rivers State, particularly in oil-producing communities. It employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis. The quantitative analysis combined descriptive statistics, such as percentages, with inferential statistics, such as Chi-square, which are measures of association. Qualitative data were analysed using thematic and content analysis. The main finding was that there is a significant impact on the environment, economy, and health in the core Niger Delta due to the high volume of gas flared and the associated carbon emissions resulting from the failure to enforce zero-gas flaring.

Keywords: Gas Flaring, Policy, Environmental, Niger Delta, Nigeria

Introduction

Gas flaring linked to crude oil production in Nigeria began under British colonial rule when Shell started oil extraction in 1958. As oil production increased, so did the volume of gas flared during the process. In Nigeria alone, approximately 23 billion cubic metres of gas are flared annually at over 100 flare sites, accounting for more than 13 per cent of the world's total gas flaring out of over 150 billion cubic metres of natural gas vented and flared each year. This results in greenhouse gas emissions of 45 million tonnes of CO₂, accounting for 11% of the global total of 400 million tonnes annually. As a consequence, Nigeria lost around \$72 billion in revenue from 1970 to 2006 due to gas flaring. Currently, Nigeria forfeits about \$2.5 billion annually due to flaring of associated gas (Kaldany, 2006). For instance, in 2011 alone,

¹**Acknowledgement:** This is to acknowledge the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND) for providing the funding for this research under the 2021 TETFUND Institution-Based Research (IBR) with Reference No: FUO/AP/TETF.24IBR/001. The contributions of the three research assistants are also well appreciated.

international oil companies flared 619,032,858 standard cubic feet (scf) of associated gas, representing 25.79 per cent of their total gas production (NNPC, 2011; Aniche, 2015).

Flaring of associated gas releases a greenhouse gas (GHG) that contributes to global warming and climate change, with flaring emissions currently estimated at 400 million tonnes of carbon dioxide annually. Globally, flaring and venting gas during petroleum production waste a valuable energy resource valued at approximately 30.6 billion dollars each year and harm the environment (Aniche, 2015). The paradox is that the volume of gas flared each year in Nigeria could meet the country's energy needs and help resolve the energy crisis (Agboola, Nwulu, Egelioglu, and Agboola, 2011).

Although the environmental impact of gas flaring is transboundary or global in terms of global warming and climate change, it has some negative effects on the immediate or local environment (Christensen & Haugland, 2001). For example, flares contain as many as 250 toxins, and flares emit particulate matter including sulphur dioxide, nitrogen dioxide, and carcinogenic substances, as well as unburned fuel, hydrogen sulphide, and several other substances that can cause aggravated asthma, cough, chronic bronchitis, decreased lung function, difficulty or painful breathing, and premature death. Flares create acid rain that corrodes metal roofs, acidifies lakes and streams, and kills vegetation. Ibeanu (2008) also points out that flaring gas near human dwellings promotes acid rain, devastates farmland and fishing waters, leads to deforestation and wildlife destruction, and threatens resource flows and livelihoods (Nwankwo & Ogagarue, 2011).

By the late 1970s and mid-1980s, the Nigerian government, in an effort to reduce gas flaring, enacted various policies and laws imposing fines on oil majors based on the amount of gas flared during oil production. Besides fining international oil companies (IOCs) for gas flaring, the Nigerian government set multiple deadlines for eliminating gas flaring, but none of these zero-gas-flaring targets has been met. Economically, and perhaps paradoxically, the revenue generated from oil is less than the annual loss due to gas flaring, in terms of environmental damage, energy waste, and the depletion of agricultural and human resources. However, the government appears more focused on maximising short-term oil revenues rather than committing to long-term efforts to eliminate gas flaring altogether. In other words, the Nigerian government is not willing to make the short-term sacrifice of losing some oil revenue necessary to achieve zero gas flaring. As a result, the government prioritises immediate gains over future benefits (Agboola et al, 2011; Kingston, 2011).

Thus, the Nigerian government and its oil-sector agency, NNPC, are much more focused on increasing oil export revenue through higher oil production than on strictly aligning oil production with the capacity of gas utilisation facilities. Meanwhile, oil multinationals invest more in boosting oil output to maximise profits rather than in expanding the capacity of gas utilisation facilities. Consequently, Nigeria has only managed to enforce a marginal reduction in gas flaring. Therefore, joint venture partners and other oil companies prioritise increasing oil production for higher revenues or profits over expanding the capacity of gas utilisation facilities. Nevertheless, this study aims to systematically analyse the environmental, economic, and health implications of failing to enforce zero-gas flaring in the Niger Delta, Nigeria.

Literature Review

The Implications of the Failure of Enforcement of the Zero Gas Flaring Policy in Nigeria

Numerous efforts have been undertaken by the Nigerian government to reduce and eliminate gas flaring, including gas re-injection policies, fines for gas flaring, and deadlines for zero gas flaring for oil multinationals since 1984. However, the failure to meet these deadlines or the postponement of deadlines due to the Nigerian government's inability to enforce compliance among oil multinationals operating in joint ventures with the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), coupled with the environmental, economic, and health implications of this enforcement failure, has attracted scholarly attention. Bassey (2008) and Walker (2011) observe that the politics surrounding gas flaring have led to the shifting of the official end dates for gas flaring, as it suits the interests of the international oil corporations (IOCs) and the government, with the revised deadline announced in November 2007—about a month before the original 2008 deadline. Subsequently, these deadlines have been shifted multiple times, from 2008 to 2009, then to 2011, and again to 2012.

Bassey (2008) and Walker (2011) note that the politics of gas flaring have led to repeated shifts in the deadlines for ending gas flares, often to suit the interests of the international oil corporations (IOCs) and the government. A new deadline was announced in November 2007, about a month before the existing 2008 deadline. Since then, there have been further shifts from 2008 to 2009, then to 2011, and subsequently to 2012.

Thus, Bassey (2008), Aghalino (2009), Ogbara (2009), Osuoka (2009), Babatunde (2010), Buzcu-Guven, Harriss and Hertzemark (2010), Farina (2011), Kingston (2011), Oluduro (2011) and Ukala (2011) based their studies on the insincerity of the oil multinationals to meet the zero-gas deadlines, the inability of the NNPC to finance its part of the joint venture partnerships with the oil multinationals, and the Nigerian government's incapacity to enforce the gas flare-out regime. Ibeanu (2008) outlined the environmental effects of gas flaring in Nigeria.

However, systematic investigation into the impacts of failing to enforce zero-gas flaring on the environment, economy, and health of the core Niger Delta has not been sufficiently explored by scholars. In other words, a thorough examination of the environmental, economic, and health implications related to the specific amount of gas flared and the resulting carbon emissions in the core Niger Delta remains inadequately addressed in scholarly work.

Thus, Bassey (2008), Aghalino (2009), Ogbara (2009), Osuoka (2009), Babatunde (2010), Buzcu-Guven, Harriss and Hertzemark (2010), Farina (2011), Kingston (2011), Oluduro (2011), and Ukala (2011) based their studies on the insincerity of the oil multinationals to comply with the zero-gas deadlines, the inability of the NNPC to finance its share of joint venture partnerships with oil multinationals, and the incapacity of the Nigerian government to enforce the gas flare-out regime. Ibeanu (2008) outlined the environmental effects of gas flaring in Nigeria.

However, systematic investigation into the impacts of failing to enforce zero-gas flaring on the environment, economy, and health of the core Niger Delta has not yet been sufficiently undertaken by scholars. In other words, a thorough examination of the environmental, economic, and health consequences associated with the specific amounts of gas flared and the resulting carbon emissions in the core Niger Delta remains lacking in academic attention. In light of this, this study aims to investigate the extent of the environmental, economic, and health implications

of the particular quantities of gas flared and the emitted carbon in the core Niger Delta of Nigeria.

The Rentier Character of the Nigerian State and the Failure of Enforcement of the Zero Gas Regime

This study will primarily focus on the theory of the rentier state. According to Beblawi and Luciani (1987), a rentier state is a term used to describe those states that derive all or a significant portion of their revenues from the rent of indigenous resources to external clients, thereby fostering a rentier mentality and a rentier class within these states. For Mahdavy (1970), rentier states are typically endowed with abundant mineral resources such as oil and gas and therefore depend largely on rent-seeking, which involves earning income by capturing economic rent through manipulation or exploitation rather than generating profits through economic transactions and the production of additional wealth.

The theory of the rentier state suggests that countries that regularly receive large amounts of oil revenue from abroad tend to become autonomous from their societies, unaccountable to their citizens, and often autocratic. It is therefore used to explain why Iran, along with other Gulf states and some African nations such as Nigeria, Gabon, and Angola, with abundant resource wealth, performs less well than their resource-poor counterparts (Mahdavy, 1970; Schwarz, 2007).

Beblawi (1990) identifies four key characteristics of a rentier state: (a) rent opportunities must dominate, indicating that a purely rentier economy does not exist; (b) the rent must originate from abroad or outside the country; (c) in a rentier state, only a small elite (the rentier class) is involved in generating rent, while the majority participate in its distribution and consumption. This means that government officials or political leaders (the rentier class) negotiate deals, collect revenue, and allocate it to the public, who are not involved in wealth creation; and (d) the government must be the primary recipient of external rent, meaning the rents accrue directly to the government.

The implications of the above characterisation are that rentierism often transforms rentier states into mono-product or mono-cultural economies where (i) the limited productive activities are mainly confined to the level of primary production necessary for oil exploration, (ii) the public sector predominates over the private sector, and (iii) within the private sector, the informal sector dominates the formal sector. Beblawi (1990), thus, notes that this state of affairs creates a “rentier mentality”.

Similarly, Luciani (1990) points out that rentierism is associated with the rise of weak states, where high levels of rentierism can harm the modern state's ability to represent its citizens or fulfil its representative role. Rentierism shifts a rent-seeking state into an allocation or distributive state rather than a production state (Anderson, 1987). A production state depends on taxing the domestic economy for revenue, whereas an allocation state does not rely on domestic sources because external rents free it from the necessity to extract income locally (Moore, 2004; Ifesinachi, 2007; Khouri, 2008).

The Nigerian state is indeed a rent-seeking state that relies on oil revenue from rents or royalties paid by oil and gas multinationals for their exploration and exploitation activities in Nigeria. For

instance, oil and gas constitute nearly 90% of Nigeria's revenue and foreign exchange earnings, demonstrating that Nigeria has a mono-product or mono-cultural economy in which oil forms the economic backbone. Rents, therefore, dominate Nigeria's economy. Accordingly, the Nigerian state meets all the characteristics outlined by Hazim Beblawi, qualifying it as a rentier state, specifically a rentier-oil state. In Nigeria, for example, rents or royalties are collected directly by the Nigerian state, with only a few individuals, namely government officials, involved in their generation; the remainder are engaged in their distribution. The implications of this are that the Nigerian state functions primarily as an allocator or distributive entity rather than a producer. Even the limited productive activities in Nigeria are concentrated at the primary level, chiefly the exploration and production of oil and gas (i.e., the upstream oil sector) by multinational corporations.

Therefore, the analytical utility and usefulness of rentierism in this study stem from the fact that it more than any other theory captures the very essence of the political economy of the non-enforcement of the gas flare-out regime in Nigeria, as well as the fundamental and primary concerns of the joint venture partners, like the Nigerian government represented by NNPC and oil multinationals. Rentier state theory has high analytical value, as it is adequate and apt for explaining the Nigerian state's role in the poor enforcement of the zero gas flaring policy. The failure to enforce the zero-gas flaring regime by the Nigerian state is illustrated by the four main contradictions of the joint venture partners in Nigeria identified by rentier state theory, such as (a) contradiction between rents or revenues and the environment, (b) conflict between profits and the environment, (c) tension between national security and environmental security, and (d) contradiction between increased oil production and the efficient utilisation of natural resources. In summary, there is a conflict between economic diplomacy and environmental diplomacy.

For example, contradictions between rents and the environment, conflicts between profits and the environment, contradictions between increased oil production and the efficient use of natural resources, and tensions between national security and environmental or local community security explain why the Nigerian state prioritises increased oil production and revenues over the environmental damage caused by gas flaring in the Niger Delta.

Due to the rentier nature of the Nigerian state and the associated rentier mentality of Nigeria's rentier class, Nigeria prioritises the collection of oil revenues in the form of rents or royalties over protecting the environment in oil communities in the Niger Delta. The implication of this is that a country that relies heavily on oil revenue to cover its expenditures cannot genuinely enforce a zero gas flaring deadline on oil and gas multinationals. The main concern of the Nigerian state is to increase oil revenues through higher production, without regard for the capacity of the associated gas gathering facilities, at the expense of oil communities. The Nigerian government and its oil-sector agencies, such as NNPC, are much more focused on boosting oil export revenue through increased oil production than on limiting oil production to the capacity of related gas utilisation facilities or on the funds available to meet the flare-out target.

From the foregoing, therefore, rentier state theory helps us understand that in rentier oil states, the main concern is increasing crude oil production, albeit for different reasons. For example, in the Nigerian state and its agency, NNPC, the goal is to increase oil revenues, which are seen as

essential for national security. Meanwhile, for oil multinationals operating in Nigeria, the aim is to maximise profits. Under these circumstances, policies such as achieving zero-gas flaring and eliminating the environmental, economic, and health impacts of gas flaring in the Niger Delta remain largely rhetorical and secondary.

The Methods

The research design used in this study is primarily a survey design, specifically descriptive research involving a sample survey, a questionnaire, a quantitative approach, a correlational study, and a case study. In other words, the study is a descriptive survey. The focus of this study will be on the core Niger Delta region, comprising three states: Bayelsa, Delta, and Rivers, all in Nigeria. The communities within these states are mainly oil-producing areas that experience the direct environmental, economic, and health impacts of Nigeria's failure to implement a zero-gas flaring regime.

Figure 1: A Map of Oil Fields in the Core Niger-Delta

Source: Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (2022). *Nigerian Oil Industry Handbook and Directory*. Abuja: NNPC.

The recent census conducted in Nigeria by the National Population Commission (NPC) in 2006 shows that the combined population of the three core Niger Delta states is (NPC 2006). However, due to the scope, focus, and nature of this study, our population will be limited to residents in the oil-producing communities of these states. To enhance accuracy, validity, and precision, and to reduce costs and time, our sample size will be 0.01% of the population, amounting to 1,000 respondents; with 200 from Bayelsa State, 400 from Delta State, and 400 from Rivers State, based on their respective populations (see Table 1). For sampling techniques, we will employ probability sampling, specifically simple random sampling. A total of 30 participants will be purposively selected for interviews, with 10 participants from each state.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents from the Three States (N = 1000)

States	Number of Participants	Percentage Number of Participants
Bayelsa	200	20
Delta	400	40
Rivers	400	40
Total	1000	100

Source: Fieldwork 2025

The instruments used for data collection in this research are a questionnaire and an interview schedule, both self-report techniques. The field survey conducted in May 2025 involved collecting primary data through face-to-face distribution and administration of a structured questionnaire. This approach helped build rapport, improve response reliability, and achieve a high response rate by addressing participants' concerns or requests for clarification. The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended questions that enabled respondents to evaluate various statements related to the research objectives. Responses were recorded on a five-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UND), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). Additionally, face-to-face interviews were conducted in July 2025.

To ensure efficient distribution and retrieval, three research assistants were engaged to cover the purposively selected three federal universities in the South-South region. These assistants played a crucial role in facilitating communication with respondents and ensuring a smooth data collection process. Of the 1000 questionnaires distributed, 909 were successfully retrieved, resulting in a response rate of approximately 90.9% (see Table 2).

Table 2: Questionnaire Distribution

Questionnaire	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1. Distributed	1000	100
2. Returned	909	90.9
3. Not Returned	74	7.4
4. Rejected/Invalid	17	1.7

Source: Fieldwork 2025.

The instrument was validated for face or content validity through expert opinion or jury review. In other words, we will seek the opinion or judgment of experts in the field of social and political research to determine whether the questionnaire contains appropriate questions or measures what it intends to measure. The aim is to ensure that differences in scores genuinely reflect differences among individuals or respondents. The instrument will also be tested for reliability, consistency, dependability, and credibility using external methods, specifically the Test-Retest (T-R) method. The expectation is that, when the test is administered twice on the same sample, a high correlation coefficient will indicate reliability.

The methods of data gathering for this study are mixed-method, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques known as methodological triangulation. Similarly, the data analysis methods are mixed-method, combining quantitative and qualitative-descriptive

approaches, again referred to as methodological triangulation. The study utilises a combination of descriptive statistical analysis, classified as measures of relativity such as percentages, and inferential statistical analysis, classified as measures of association such as Chi-square, to analyse the quantitative data. Meanwhile, qualitative data from interviews are analysed using thematic analysis, and documentary data are examined through qualitative content analysis.

The Results

This section examines the environmental, economic, and health implications of the failure to enforce zero-gas flaring in the Niger Delta, Nigeria, by analysing responses to survey items to test the hypothesis.

H₀: The failure of the enforcement of zero-gas flaring has no significant impacts on the environment, economy, and health of the people of the Niger Delta, Nigeria.

H₁: The failure of the enforcement of zero-gas flaring has significant impacts on the environment, economy, and health of the people of the Niger Delta, Nigeria.

Table 3: Responses for Zero Gas Regime Enforcement and Implications

S/No	Items of the Questionnaire	SA	A	UND	D	SD
1.	The failure to enforce the zero gas flaring regime has continued to unleash environmental hazards in the Niger Delta region.	793	57	16	29	14
2.	Gas flaring has negative environmental impacts in oil-producing areas, including acid rain and roof leaks.	798	52	13	31	15
3.	The non-implementation of the zero gas flaring has continued to cause serious health risks in the Niger Delta.	799	51	18	28	13
4.	The continuous flaring of gas is linked to an increase in various diseases, such as respiratory diseases.	801	49	15	30	14
5.	The continuous shifts in the gas flaring deadlines constitute massive economic waste.	796	54	11	32	16
6.	The low utilisation of associated gas is a significant source of energy waste.	801	51	14	26	17

Source: Fieldwork 2025.

Note: SA=Strongly Agree; A=Agree; UND=Undecided; D=Disagree; SD=Strongly Disagree.

Using the figures from the respondents' answers in the questionnaire in Table 3, we determined the crosstabulation of observed cases, expected cases, and simple percentages with the help of SPSS (see Table 4).

Table 4: Crosstabulation

Items	Item_1	Count	Responses					Total
			A	D	SA	SD	UND	
		Count	57	29	793	14	16	909
		Expected Count	56.5	31.7	789.2	16.0	15.6	909.0
		% within Items	6.3%	3.2%	87.2%	1.5%	1.8%	100.0%

Item_2	% within Responses	18.2%	16.5%	18.1%	15.7%	18.4%	18.0%
	% of Total	1.1%	0.6%	15.7%	0.3%	0.3%	18.0%
	Count	52	31	798	15	13	909
	Expected Count	56.5	31.7	789.2	16.0	15.6	909.0
Item_3	% within Items	5.7%	3.4%	87.8%	1.7%	1.4%	100.0%
	% within Responses	16.6%	17.6%	18.2%	16.9%	14.9%	18.0%
	% of Total	1.0%	0.6%	15.8%	0.3%	0.3%	18.0%
	Count	51	28	799	13	18	909
Item_4	Expected Count	56.5	31.7	789.2	16.0	15.6	909.0
	% within Items	5.6%	3.1%	87.9%	1.4%	2.0%	100.0%
	% within Responses	16.2%	15.9%	18.2%	14.6%	20.7%	18.0%
	% of Total	1.0%	0.6%	15.8%	0.3%	0.4%	18.0%
Item_5	Count	49	30	801	14	15	909
	Expected Count	56.5	31.7	789.2	16.0	15.6	909.0
	% within Items	5.4%	3.3%	88.1%	1.5%	1.7%	100.0%
	% within Responses	15.6%	17.0%	18.3%	15.7%	17.2%	18.0%
Item_6	% of Total	1.0%	0.6%	15.8%	0.3%	0.3%	18.0%
	Count	54	32	796	16	11	909
	Expected Count	56.5	31.7	789.2	16.0	15.6	909.0
	% within Items	5.9%	3.5%	87.6%	1.8%	1.2%	100.0%
Item_6	% within Responses	17.2%	18.2%	18.1%	18.0%	12.6%	18.0%
	% of Total	1.1%	0.6%	15.7%	0.3%	0.2%	18.0%
	Count	51	26	401	17	14	509
	Expected Count	31.6	17.7	441.9	9.0	8.8	509.0
Total	% within Items	10.0%	5.1%	78.8%	3.3%	2.8%	100.0%
	% within Responses	16.2%	14.8%	9.1%	19.1%	16.1%	10.1%
	% of Total	1.0%	0.5%	7.9%	0.3%	0.3%	10.1%
	Count	314	176	4388	89	87	5054
Total	Expected Count	314.0	176.0	4388.0	89.0	87.0	5054.0
	% within Items	6.2%	3.5%	86.8%	1.8%	1.7%	100.0%
	% within Responses	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	6.2%	3.5%	86.8%	1.8%	1.7%	100.0%

Source: SPSS, 2025.

Using the figures from respondents' questionnaire responses in Table 3, we calculated the Chi-Square Statistics with SPSS (see Table 5).

Table 5: SPSS Output of Chi-Square Hypothesis Testing

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	36.419 ^a	20	.014
Likelihood Ratio	32.507	20	.038
N of Valid Cases	5054		

$\alpha = 0.05$.

Source: SPSS, 2025.

The results in Table 5 show a chi-square value of 36.419 and a p-value of 0.014. Testing the hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level, the p-value of 0.014 is less than the alpha value (α) of 0.05; therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is supported, stating that the failure to enforce zero-gas flaring has significantly impacted the environment, economy, and health of the people of the Niger Delta, Nigeria. This result is confirmed by a simple percentage descriptive analysis of the total responses, where 86.8 per cent of respondents strongly agreed (SA), 6.2 per cent agreed (A), 1.7 per cent were undecided (U), 3.5 per cent disagreed (D), and 1.8 per cent strongly disagreed (SD), as shown in Table 4.

Discussion of the Results

The Chi-Square Test indicated that the failure to enforce zero-gas flaring has significantly impacted the environment, economy, and health of the people of the Niger Delta, Nigeria. This result is confirmed by a simple percentage descriptive analysis of the total responses. Oil majors in Nigeria have consistently reported difficulties in meeting the 1984 deadline, citing a lack of finance to construct a gas re-injection plant within the timeframe. As a result, the deadline was extended to 1985, yet oil companies failed to adhere to the provisions, claiming it was too expensive to re-inject gas. Oil multinationals rejected the 2004 zero gas flaring deadline as unrealistic and blamed the government for not consulting them when setting the deadline. On its part, Shell announced that it would eliminate gas flaring from its oil fields in 2008. Again, the Nigerian government was persuaded to drop the 2004 deadline and adopt the 2008 deadline, as recommended by oil multinationals. Once again, the 2008 deadline, agreed upon with the oil companies, was not supported by any new legislation or formal regulation. Because it was not legally binding, the deadline was vulnerable to violations (Aniche, 2015a). Not surprisingly, oil multinationals failed to meet the deadline.

Subsequently, in 2005, Shell announced to members of the Nigerian Senate that the 2008 deadline was no longer realistic, as it had now set its target for 2009. By 2008, the Nigerian government was a bundle of contradictions, as the President and members of the Federal Executive Council (FEC) could not agree on whether the deadline was for January or December of that year (Aghalino, 2009; Ukala, 2011; Walker, 2011). Since then, the Nigerian government has been shifting zero gas flaring deadlines, for example, from 2009 to 2011 and from 2011 to 2012, and thus, gas flaring continues in Nigeria. For example, oil multinationals operating in Nigeria flared 312,488,053 standard cubic feet (scf) of associated gas, amounting to 11.25% of the total gas they produced in 2016 alone (Aniche, 2015b).

Oil multinationals in joint ventures with NNPC continue to flare gas in oil fields, and there is little on the ground to suggest that they will end gas flaring soon. In other words, the oil multinationals are still flaring associated gas in Nigeria and have consistently failed to comply with the zero gas flaring deadline, leading to repeated shifts from 2003 to 2004, then to 2008, 2009, 2011, 2012, and finally to 2020. The result is that zero gas flaring in Nigeria remains elusive, as the government sets new deadlines each year to entirely stop flaring (see Figures 2, 3,

4, & 5 in the Appendix for pictorial views of flare sites in the Niger Delta). The bottom line is that the Nigerian government has not been successful in enforcing these deadlines on oil multinationals. The core issue is that the government has not been fully committed or sincere in ensuring compliance, fearing a loss of oil revenues. A serious government would have linked oil production to the capacity for gas utilisation, even if it meant reducing oil output and revenue (Aniche, 2015c).

Other documented evidence and official publications corroborate these results. For instance, because gas flaring involves a mixture of different gases—whose composition varies by source—the practice has significant environmental and health impacts. The gases released during oil production, mainly natural gas, contain over 90% methane (CH₄), along with ethane (C₂H₆) and small amounts of other hydrocarbons; inert gases such as Nitrogen (N₂) and CO₂ may also be present. Gas flaring from refineries and other process operations typically includes a mixture of hydrocarbons and, in some cases, Hydrogen (H₂). Landfill gas, biogas, or digester gas comprises a mixture of CH₄ and CO₂, along with small quantities of other inert gases (Emam, 2015). For details about gas flare constituents or compositions, see Table 6.

Table 6: Waste Gas Compositions at a Typical Plant

Gas Flare Constituent	Minimum	Maximum	Average
Methane (CH ₄)	7.17	82.0	43.6
Ethane (C ₂ H ₆)	0.55	13.1	3.66
Propane (C ₃ H ₈)	2.04	64.2	20.3
n-Butane (C ₄ H ₁₀)	0.199	28.3	2.78
Isobutane (C ₄ H ₁₀)	1.33	57.6	14.3
n-Pentane (C ₅ H ₁₂)	0.008	3.39	0.266
Isopentane (C ₅ H ₁₂)	0.096	4.71	0.530
neo-Pentane (C ₅ H ₁₂)	0.000	0.342	0.017
n-Hexane (C ₆ H ₁₄)	0.026	3.53	0.635
Ethylene (C ₂ H ₄)	0.081	3.20	1.05
Propylene (C ₃ H ₆)	0.000	42.5	2.73
I-Butane (C ₄ H ₈)	0.000	14.7	0.696
Carbon monoxide (CO)	0.000	0.932	0.186
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	0.023	2.85	0.713

Hydrogen sulphide (H ₂ S)	0.000	3.80	0.256
Hydrogen (H ₂)	0.000	37.6	5.54
Oxygen (O ₂)	0.019	5.43	0.357
Nitrogen (N ₂)	0.073	32.2	1.30
Water (H ₂ O)	0.000	14.7	1.14

Source: Emam, E.A. (2015). Gas flaring in industry: An overview. *Petroleum & Coal*, 57(5), 532-555.

CO₂ and CH₄ are greenhouse gases that, when released directly into the atmosphere, trap heat. The climate impact is clear, indicating a significant contribution to global GHG emissions. For example, about 45.8 billion kilowatt-hours of heat are radiated into the Niger Delta atmosphere from gas flaring daily. As a result, gas flaring has increased temperatures and rendered large areas uninhabitable (for information on the implications of the distance between gas flare sites and the immediate environment of the Niger Delta, especially concerning thermal radiation, see Table 7). CO₂ emissions from flaring have a high global warming potential and contribute to climate change. About 75% of CO₂ emissions originate solely from the combustion of fossil fuels. CH₄ is actually more harmful than CO₂; it has approximately 25 times greater global warming potential on a mass basis. It is also more prevalent in flares that burn at lower efficiency (Odjugo, 2010; Ismail & Umukoro, 2012; Emam, 2015).

Table 7: Thermal and Noise Emissions from Gas Flaring at Distance

Distance (metres)	Thermal Radiation (kw/m ²)	Noise Level (decibels)
10	5.66	86.3 20 5.87 86.19
30	6.04	86.02 40 6.14 85.78
50	6.17	85.50 60 6.14 85.18
70	6.04	84.83 80 5.88 84.46
90	5.67	84.08 100 5.42 83.68

Source: Emam, E.A. (2015). Gas flaring in industry: An overview. *Petroleum & Coal*, 57(5), 532-555.

The health implications of the failure to enforce the zero gas flaring regime in Nigeria are massive, as indicated in Tables 8 and 9.

Table 8: The Possible Amount or Volume of VOCs and PAHs in Gas Flare

VOCs	Amount (mg/m ³)	PAHs	Amount (mg/m ³)
Acetylene	53.7	Acenaphthene	2.9
Benzene	144.5	Acenaphthylene	23.2

Ethylene	29.0	Anthracene	42.1
Hexane	8.5	Benz(a)Anthracene	17.3
Naphthalene	99.4	Benzo(g,h,i)Fluoranthene	10.2
Styrene	75.5	Chrysene	2.2
Toluene	18.2	Fluoranthene	51.4
Xylene	29.8	Pyrene	32.4

Source: Strosher, M. (1996). *Investigation of Flare Gas Emissions in Alberta*, Alberta: Alberta Research Council.

Table 9: Some of the Hazardous Health Effects of the Gas Flare Substances

Compound	Health Effects	Volume of Acceptable Daily Intake
Benzene	Haematological neoplasm and blood disorder, including reduced number of red blood cells and aplastic anaemia, pancytopenia, and leukaemia	Not established, but toxicant at any level
Naphthalene	Destroying the membrane of the red blood cells with the liberation of haemoglobin, cataracts, headache, confusion, excitement, malaise, profuse sweating, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, irritation of the bladder	0-096 ug/m ³
Styrene	Irritant of the skin, eyes, and mucous membranes and central nervous system effects	Not established
Toluene	Central nervous system effects, which lead to narcosis, incoordination, emotional liability, headache, and fatigue.	0.12 ug/m ³
Xylene	Central nervous system effects which lead to delayed development, decreased fetal body weight and altered enzyme activities	0.12 ug/m ³

Source: USEPA 2003 in Ishinone, M. (2004) "Gas Flaring in the Niger Delta: The Potential Benefits to its Reduction on the Local Economy and Environment" Retrieved from <http://nature.berkeley.edu/classes> on 21/09/2012.

Conclusion and Recommendations

We noted that Nigeria is one of the countries with the highest levels of gas flaring, featuring more than 1000 gas flaring points that release over 23 billion cubic metres of gas annually, with only 19% of the total gas flared recovered (Audu, 2013). Due to the rentier nature of the Nigerian state, it has not been able to enforce the zero gas flaring regime. As a result, the oil

multinationals have struggled to meet the deadlines for eliminating gas flaring, leading to continual shifts in those deadlines. This has significant implications for heat radiation, global warming, and climate change.

Thus, we have achieved our objective: to investigate the impacts of the Nigerian state's failure to compel oil multinationals to comply with the zero gas flaring regime on thermal radiation, global warming, and climate change. Therefore, we concluded that the Nigerian state's failure to enforce compliance with the zero gas flaring policy on oil multinationals has significantly impacted heat radiation, global warming, and climate change.

From the foregoing, we therefore recommend that the fundamental measure, given the rentier character of the Nigerian state, is to diversify the economy's revenue base by reducing excessive dependence on oil revenue through mainstreaming other domestic sources, such as direct taxes, and developing other sectors, such as manufacturing. This is a vital and far-reaching solution that will enable the Nigerian state to de-emphasise oil revenue by limiting oil production to the gas utilisation capacity of oil multinationals, as required to meet policy deadlines. This will also push oil multinationals to adopt effective gas utilisation technologies and strategies to eliminate gas flaring.

References

- Agboola, M.O., Nwulu, N.I., Egelioglu, F. & Agboola, O.P. (2011). Gas flaring in Nigeria: Opportunity for household cooking utilisation. *International Journal of Thermal and Environment Engineering*, 2(2), 69–74.
- Aghalino, S.O. (2009). Gas flaring, environmental pollution and abatement measures in Nigeria, 1969-2001. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 11(4), 219–238.
- Anderson, L. (1987). The state in the Middle East North Africa. *Comparative Politics*, 20(1).
- Aniche, E.T. (2015a). *Oil sector and non-enforcement of zero-gas flaring policy in Nigeria*. Saarbrücken: Lambert Academic Publishing (LAP) and OmniScriptum GmbH & Co. KG.
- Aniche, E.T. (2015b). International oil corporations (IOCs), associated gas utilisation technologies and gas flare elimination strategies: Implication for zero-gas flaring regime in Nigeria. *Journal of Asian and African Social Sciences and Humanities*, 1(1), 48-64.
- Aniche, E.T. (2015c). An assessment of the role of Nigerian state in enforcing zero-gas flare regime, 1979-2012: The imperatives of environmental diplomacy. *Civil and Environmental Research*, 7(12), 29–45.
- Aniche, E.T. (2016). The devil's excreta: Assessing the impact of oil joint venture partnerships on the enforcement of zero-gas flaring regime in Nigeria. *South East Journal of Political Science (SEJPS)*, 2(1), 250–277.
- Aniche, E.T. & Egbuchulam, M.U. (2017). In danger of extinction: Interrogating the effects of the failure of enforcement of zero gas flaring regime in Nigeria. *Federal University Otuoke Journal of Political Science (FUOJPS)*, 1(1), 100–113.
- Babatunde, A. (2010). Environmental conflict and the politics of oil in oil bearing areas of Nigeria's Niger Delta. *Peace and Conflict Review*, 5(1), 1–13.

- Baker, L. (2008). Facilitating whose power? WB and IMF policy influence in Nigeria's energy sector. Retrieved from http://www.brettonwoodsprojects.org/nigeriaatissue_on_19/04/2011.
- Bassey, N. (2008). Gas flaring: Assaulting communities, jeopardising the world. A paper presented at the National Environmental Consultation hosted by the Environmental Rights Action in Conjunction with the Federal Ministry of Environment, Reiz Hotel, Abuja on December 10-11.
- Beblawi, H. (1990). Rentier state in the Arab world. In G. Luciani (Ed.) *The Arab state*. London: Routledge.
- Beblawi, H. & Luciani, G. (1987). *The rentier state*. London: Croom Helm.
- Buzcu-Guven, B., Harriss, R. & Hertzmark, D. (2010). Gas flaring and venting: Extent, impacts and remedies. In J. Barnes, et al (Eds.) *Energy market consequences of an emerging US carbon management policy, Energy Forum*. Houston: James A. Baker III Institute for Public Policy, Rice University.
- Christiansen, A.C. & Haugland, T. (2001). Gas flaring and global public goods. *The Fridtjof Nansen Institute (FNI) Report*, 20.
- Emam, E.A. (2015). Gas flaring in industry: An overview. *Petroleum & Coal*, 57(5), 532-555.
- Evoh, O. (2002). Gas flares, oil companies and politics in Nigeria. Retrieved from http://ngrguardiannews.com_on_20/09/2011.
- Farina, M.F. (2011). Flare gas reduction: Recent global trends and policy considerations. Retrieved from http://www.ge-energy.com_on_20/06/2011.
- Feldman, N. (2003). *After Jihad: American and struggle for Islamic democracy*. New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux.
- Herb, M. (2002). Does rentierism prevent democracy? A paper delivered at the Annual Meeting of the American Political Science Association, August 29 - September 1.
- Ibeanu, O. (2000). Oiling the friction: Environmental conflict management in the Niger Delta Nigeria. *An Environmental Change and Security Profile Report*, 6.
- Ibeanu, O. (2008). Affluence and affliction: The Niger-Delta as a critique of Political Science in Nigeria. Nsukka: University of Nigeria Press.
- Ifesinachi, K. (2007). The rentier state, global liberalism and citizenship in Nigeria. A paper presented at the international conference on *Globalisation: Migration, citizenship and identity*. University of Ibadan, Nigeria, November 6-9.
- Ifesinachi, K. & Aniche, E.T. (2014). Oil joint venture partnerships and Nigerian economy. *University of Nigeria Journal of Political Economy*, 7(1&2), 1-24.
- Ifesinachi, K. & Aniche, E.T. (2015). The Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) and enforcement of zero gas flaring regime in Nigeria. *ANSU Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 4(1), 48-74.
- Ifesinachi, K. & Aniche, E.T. (2016). The role of oil multinationals in the failure of zero-gas flaring policy in Nigeria. *Journal of Behavioural Sciences and Development Studies*, 3(1&2), 14-43.
- Ikelegbe, A.O. (1993). Pollution in Nigeria: Causes, effects and control: The case of Delta State. A paper presented at the 14th Annual Congress of the Nigerian Geographical Association, Minna April 18-22.
- Ishinone, M. (2004). "Gas Flaring in the Niger Delta: The Potential Benefits to its Reduction on the Local Economy and Environment" Retrieved from http://nature.berkeley.edu/classes_on_21/09/2012.
- Ismail, O.S. and Umukoro, G.E. (2012). Global impact of gas flaring. *Energy and Power Engineering*, 4, 290-302.

- Kaldany, R. (2006). Global gas flaring reduction: A time for action! A keynote speech presented at *Global forum on flaring and gas utilisation*, Paris, December 13.
- Khoury, R. (2008). Rentierism revisited. *Arab Reform Bulletin*, September.
- Kingston, K.G. (2011). The dilemmas of minerals dependent economy: The case of foreign direct investment and pollution in Nigeria. *African Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(1), 1-14.
- Luciani, G. (1990). Allocation versus production states: A theoretical framework. In G. Luciani (Ed.) *The Arab state*. London: Routledge.
- Mahdavy, H. (1970). The patterns and problems of economic development in rentier states: The case of Iran. In M.A Cook (Ed.) *Studies in economic history of Middle East*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Moore, M. (2004). Revenues, state formation and the quality of government in developing countries. *International Political Science Review*, 25(3).
- Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (2011). *Draft Annual Statistical Bulletin*. Abuja: Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC).
- Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (2022). *Nigerian Oil Industry Handbook and Directory*. Abuja: NNPC.
- Nwankwo, C.N. & Ogagarue, D.O. (2011). Effects of gas flaring on surface and ground waters in Delta State, Nigeria. *Journal of Geology and Mining Research*, 3(5), 131-136.
- Odjugo, P.A. (2010). General overview of climate change impacts in Nigeria. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 29(1), 47-55.
- Ogbara, N. (2009). Why the extant legal framework prohibiting gas flare in Nigeria did not work? A paper presented at a social action organised forum on *Gas flaring prohibition and sustainable energy future for Nigeria*, September 30, Bolton White Hotels, Abuja.
- Okafor, J.C. & Aniche, E.T. (2016). Nigeria and World Bank Global Gas Flaring Reduction (GGFR) partnership: The tragedy of the commons. *Developing Country Studies*, 6(12), 44-57.
- Okonta, I. and Douglas, O. (2001). *Where vultures feast: Forty years of Shell in the Niger Delta*. Benin: ERA/FOEN.
- Oluduro, O. (2011). Bureaucratic rhetoric of climate change in Nigeria: International aspiration versus local realities. Retrieved from http://www.iucnael.org/en/documents_on_11/02/2012.
- Onosode, G. (2003). Environmental issues and the challenge of the Niger Delta: Perspectives from the Niger Delta. In *the environmental survey process*. Yaba: The CIBN Press.
- Orimoogunje, O.O., Ayanlade, A., Akinkuolie, T.A. & Odiong, A.U. (2010). Perception on effect of gas flaring on the environment. *Research Journal of Environmental and Earth Sciences*, 2(4), 188–193.
- Osuoka, I. (2009). *Flame of hell: Gas flaring in the Niger Delta*. Port Harcourt: Social Development Integrated Centre (Social Action).
- Schwarz, R. (2007). Rentier states and International Relations Theory. A paper presented at the Six Pan-European Conference on International Relations, *The place of the Middle East in International Relations: Making sense of global interconnection and local dynamics in Middle East politics*, Turin, September 12-15.
- Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) (2005). *Information Handbook*. Abuja: SPDC.
- Smith, B. (2004). Oil wealth and regime survival in the developing world: 1960-1999. *American Journal of Political Science*, 48(2).
- Strosher, M. (1996). *Investigation of Flare Gas Emissions in Alberta*, Alberta: Alberta Research Council.

- Ukala, E. (2011). Gas flaring in Nigeria’s Niger Delta: Failed promises and reviving community voices. *Journal of Energy, Climate and Environment*, 97, 97-126.
- Walker, A. (2011). Nigeria’s gas profits up in smoke. Retrieved from <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/Africa> on 28/03/2011.
- World Bank (2021). *Regulation of Associated Gas Flaring and Venting: A Global Overview and Lessons from International Experience*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group Report Number 3.

Appendix

Figures

Figure 2: An Atmospheric View of Flare Sites in the Niger Delta

World Bank (2021). *Regulation of Associated Gas Flaring and Venting: A Global Overview and Lessons from International Experience*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group Report Number 3.

Figure 3: Gas Flaring in the Oil Installation in the Gulf of Guinea

Source: Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) (2005). *Information Handbook*. Abuja: SPDC.

Figure 4: Satellite View of Gas Flaring in the Gulf of Guinea

World Bank (2021). *Regulation of Associated Gas Flaring and Venting: A Global Overview and Lessons from International Experience*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group Report Number 3.

Figure 5: A Satellite View of Flare Sites in the Niger Delta

Source: Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) (2005). *Information Handbook*. Abuja: SPDC.